

ROTATION OF OBJECTS IN A GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article provides a detailed description of determining the location of objects after rotation, set by geographical coordinates based on latitude and longitude. The solution to this problem contributes to the algorithmizing of determining the latitude and longitude of objects after rotation in Google Maps in real time. Based on this algorithm, the problem of rotating a regular network of source data directly on online Google Maps is solved in order to determine the height values of nodes of a regular network for subsequent digital terrain modeling.

Keywords: geographic coordinate system, latitude, longitude, meridian, rotation, north pole.

The task of rotating objects in a geographical coordinate system is complicated by the fact that the object of rotation has angular coordinates of latitude and longitude, unlike the Cartesian system, which has linear coordinates.

In analytical geometry, the rotation of objects is called the transformation of the coordinate system. The task of converting a coordinate system is that, knowing the coordinates of a point in one system, find its coordinates in another [1] (Fig. 1):

$$\begin{cases} x = x' \cos \alpha - y' \sin \alpha \\ y = x' \sin \alpha + y' \cos \alpha \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Transformation of the Cartesian Coordinate System

In the geographical coordinate system, the rotation of objects is complicated by the fact that it is required to pre-determine the coordinates of the latitude and longitude of the object after rotation, which is very problematic [2].

It is known that during rotation, a certain point is selected – the center of rotation, around which all the points of the object rotate. If the object and the center of rotation are set in a geographical coordinate system, therefore, the radius and angle of rotation of each point of the object are known. It is required to determine the latitude and longitude coordinates of each point of the object after rotation.

The formulation of this problem arose when compiling an algorithm for rotating a regular network of initial relief data for the tasks of engineering preparation of territories in Google Maps in real time, which contributes to preliminary and prompt decision-making on the acceptability of the project in a given area [3-5].

If there is a point O, which is the center of rotation, and a point R, which is a point on the rotating object, specified in a geographical coordinate system, located at a northern latitude on the earth's surface (see Fig. 2), then the latitudes and longitudes of points O and R are known.

Fig. 2. The rotation of point R in the geographic coordinate system.

It is known that the meridians on the Earth's surface emanate from the North Pole (in this example, point P). We can form a triangle $\triangle OPR$. Assuming that the latitude of the Northern Hemisphere is measured from the Equator towards the North Pole, we can determine the lengths of the distances OP and RP to the North Pole.

$$\begin{aligned} |OP| &= \frac{(90^\circ - O_{lat}) \cdot M}{180^\circ}; \\ |PR| &= \frac{(90^\circ - R_{lat}) \cdot M}{180^\circ}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here O_{lat} and R_{lat} are the latitude of the points O and R ;

M is the length of the Earth's meridian 20, 004, 274 m [6].

The perimeter of this triangle is known to us, and in order to rotate point R by an angle δ relative to an angle β that is still unknown, it is necessary to determine this unknown angle. To do so, we can use the sine theorem.

$$\frac{|OR|}{\alpha} = \frac{|PR|}{\beta} = \frac{|OP|}{\gamma}. \quad (2)$$

In this equation, the angle α is still unknown, which is defined as:

$$\alpha = R_{long} - O_{long} \quad (3)$$

Here R_{long} and O_{long} is the longitude of the points R and O .

Based on equation (2), we determine the angle β :

$$\beta = \frac{|PR|\alpha}{|OR|}. \quad (4)$$

Knowing the angle β , we determine the unknown angle δ' :

$$\delta' = 180^\circ - (\beta + \delta). \quad (5)$$

Here δ is the angle of rotation of the point R .

After the rotation of point R , a new triangle $\triangle OPR'$ is formed, in which the distances PO , OR' and angle δ' are known, and PR' – latitude and angle α' – longitude of point R after rotation are not known.

Based on the cosine theorem, we determine the unknown side of the triangle $\triangle OPR'$:

$$|PR'| = \sqrt{OP^2 + OR'^2 - 2|OP||OR'| \cdot \cos \delta'} \quad (6)$$

Here $OR' = OR$.

Applying the sine theorem (2), we determine the unknown angle α' :

$$\alpha' = \frac{|OR'|\delta'}{|PR'|}. \quad (7)$$

The latitude of the point R' will be:

$$R'_{lat} = 90^\circ - \left(\frac{|PR'| \cdot 180^\circ}{M} \right).$$

The longitude of the point R' is equal to:

$$R'_{long} = O_{long} + \alpha'. \quad (8)$$

Based on the sequence of the above calculations, an algorithm was developed for rotating the points of nodes of a regular network of source data in a geographical coordinate system in the Python and JavaScript programming languages with Google Maps integration.

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